

Policy Brief 2

Enhancing Media Literacy and Digital Skills Interventions for Diverse Target Groups

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Background

The REMEDIS project, funded by the European Union's CHANSE programme, conducted [evaluations of twelve distinct media literacy and digital skills \(ML&DS\) interventions](#) across six countries. These interventions targeted a wide array of groups, including **parents, educators, youth, and elderly individuals**, with a focus on fostering digital inclusion and enhancing media literacy. The results of these interventions provide valuable insights for improving the effectiveness of digital literacy programmes. This policy brief offers recommendations for practitioners and policymakers based on the findings of these evaluations.

Findings and implications

The interventions yielded varied outcomes across different demographics, with some common themes and challenges emerging. Programmes aimed at **parents** demonstrated increased confidence in managing their children's online activities, particularly in areas concerning internet safety, social media uses, and cyberbullying. Despite these improvements, many parents continued to struggle with more nuanced tasks, such as identifying misinformation and critically evaluating online content. These findings suggest that while parental interventions can enhance confidence, they need to incorporate more advanced digital literacy components to address these persistent gaps.

A key innovation emerging from the REMEDIS project is the development of the **REMEDIS Toolkit**. This comprehensive toolkit provides a **step-by-step framework** for evaluating media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) interventions. Designed to address the challenges practitioners face, the toolkit offers **guidance** on needs analysis, setting evaluation criteria, designing research, selecting samples, choosing appropriate methods, and ensuring ethical standards. The toolkit equips educators, policymakers, and practitioners with the tools needed to implement and refine ML&DS interventions effectively. Additionally, the toolkit emphasizes the importance of collaboration with organizations and research universities for complex project implementation. The guiding principles and structured approach of the toolkit ensure that interventions are **grounded in evidence and tailored to the specific needs** of diverse target groups. This innovation supports more robust evaluation, continuous improvement, and the sustainability of media literacy and digital skills programs.

Interventions designed for **educators**, including in-service teachers, showed **significant improvements** in information navigation skills and the ability to integrate digital tools into their teaching practices. However, these programmes also highlighted the importance of offering **tailored support** that reflects the varying levels of digital proficiency among educators. Ensuring that teachers have access to ongoing training and adaptable instructional resources is crucial for sustaining these gains in digital competence.

For **youth**, particularly vocational school students, interventions focused on **enhancing critical evaluation skills and multi-literacy** yielded **modest yet positive outcomes**. Students demonstrated an improved ability to recognize the motivations behind digital content, such as influencer marketing and social media posts. However, the impact on their overall digital knowledge was less pronounced, indicating that these programmes must be

more immersive and sustained to achieve deeper learning outcomes. The findings underscore the necessity of integrating media literacy education into the regular curriculum to ensure consistent engagement and skill development.

The **elderly participants** in these interventions showed **notable improvements in basic digital skills**, such as navigating online services and managing privacy settings. Nevertheless, they continued to face challenges related to social media use and the identification of misinformation. These difficulties emphasize the **need for hands-on, interactive training sessions that are paced appropriately** for older learners. The success of these interventions often depended on the quality and engagement of the instructors. In cases where language barriers or low literacy levels were prevalent, the presence of co-instructors or assistants proved essential in ensuring the effectiveness of the sessions.

One overarching challenge identified across all interventions was the **low participation rate**, which limited the generalizability of the findings. This issue highlights the importance of developing robust evaluation tools and frameworks that can capture the impact of interventions more accurately, even with smaller sample sizes. Moreover, the need for longitudinal studies to track the long-term effects of these programmes remains critical for understanding their sustained impact.

Recommendations for practitioners

To **enhance the effectiveness** of ML&DS interventions, practitioners should **focus on tailoring** their programmes to meet the specific needs of each target group. For **parents**, interventions should go beyond basic digital safety and include **strategies for identifying misinformation** and promoting critical media engagement. This can be achieved through interactive workshops that combine real-life examples, group discussions, and hands-on exercises.

For **elderly participants**, it is essential to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Sessions should be structured with regular breaks and incorporate **practical, step-by-step guidance**. Instructors should be trained to address the unique challenges faced by older learners, such as language barriers or low digital literacy. In cases where these challenges are significant, involving co-instructors or assistants can make a substantial difference in the participants' learning experience.

In programmes for **educators**, the training should be **adaptable to different levels of digital proficiency**. Teachers need ongoing access to resources and support that help them integrate digital tools effectively into their teaching. Pre-assessments can be used to gauge the specific needs of participants, ensuring that the training content is relevant and impactful.

Practitioners should also consider gender balance when designing interventions. The predominance of female participants in the parental programmes indicates a need to develop strategies that attract more male participants. Offering workshops at workplaces during lunch breaks or at community venues such as sports clubs may help achieve a more balanced participation.

Recommendations for policymakers

Policymakers play a crucial role in supporting the scalability and sustainability of ML&DS interventions. Investing in inclusive digital training initiatives is essential, particularly for disadvantaged groups such as refugees, the unemployed, and lower socio-economic status populations. By embedding ML&DS initiatives within broader educational and social policies, governments can ensure that these programmes are accessible and effective.

Developing and standardizing robust evaluation frameworks is another critical area for policy intervention. Effective evaluation tools are necessary to measure the impact of ML&DS programmes accurately. These tools should be designed to **accommodate the challenges of low participation rates** and ensure that both immediate and long-term outcomes are captured. Funding for longitudinal studies will further enhance the understanding of how these interventions impact digital inclusion and wellbeing over time.

Policymakers should also **promote the development of user-friendly toolkits** that practitioners can customize to different target groups. These toolkits should include best practices, adaptable curricula, and guidelines for evaluating intervention outcomes. Facilitating knowledge sharing across regions and sectors will help ensure that successful strategies are disseminated widely and adapted to local contexts.

Conclusion

The findings from the REMEDIS project provide a clear **roadmap** for improving ML&DS interventions. By tailoring programmes to the needs of specific demographics, engaging skilled instructors, and developing robust evaluation frameworks, practitioners and policymakers can enhance digital literacy and foster greater digital inclusion. These efforts are essential for bridging the digital divide and promoting a more informed and resilient society.

Contact information

For further details about the REMEDIS project or to access evaluation tools and resources, please check our website and social media:

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